

Common Functionalities and Applications of the Solar Energy System

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

ABSTRACT

The purpose of this review paper is to collect a comprehensive information towards the common functionalities and applications of the solar energy system. Solar energy is the production of sunlight, which can be used in the most part of human life. Sunlight is an abundant source and can be easily convert to the usable form of solar energy. Whenever sunlight irradiates the surface of specific materials such as solar heaters or panels leads to the generation of heat or electricity. To increase efficiency of the solar energy solar panels must be design with different shape and located such a way to absorb most part of the incident sunlight. In this study, functionalities of the solar energy system such as passive and active solar panels, efficiency, and its working principle have been presented. This review paper indicates that solar energy system can be design as passive or active. In passive system only thermal mass materials are used but active system needs to some equipment. Furthermore, for designing of an effective active system, cost, accuracy-sensor, reliability and efficiency factors must be considered. Moreover, some common applications of the solar energy that can be used in industries as electrical and heating energies have been reported. Meanwhile, solar energies are used depend on the requirement for water heating, heating of the building space, water distillation, water pumping and drying purposes. Data of this study has been collected from varies international scientific journals, online website and libraries textbooks.

Keywords: SUNLIGHT, ELECTRICITY, HEAT, SOLAR PANELS

Introduction

Sunlight is the most responsible source for the earth energy. Solar energy is one of the earth energy, which can be produced on the base of sunlight. Moreover, sun emits light and heat in the form of electromagnetic radiation, which leads to the creation of solar energy. With the help of technology, it is possible to capture this electromagnetic radiation and convert into the usable solar energy forms such as electrical or heating energy (Mishchenko, et al, 2006).

Calculation of the sun radiation shows that the solar energy value on the earth's surface in 24h is roughly 102,000 TW. Even though the solar energy amount is more than the requirement using amount of energy but its density is low and it refers to the season, location, which creates problem in the development of solar energy. The most important factor for the technical and economic issue of the solar energy is the available sunlight, wherever to be placed solar heaters or panels to radiate. Meanwhile, there are many factors, which must be put into consideration during the determination of efficiency of the solar energy in a given location, such as geographic location, season, local weather, local landscape and time of the day (Iqbal, Muhammad, 2012).

Naturally, sunlight to reach to the earth's surface has to cross the earth's atmosphere, which containing of the air molecules, clouds, water vapor, dust and pollutants. Therefore, it divides into three parts absorption, scattering and reflection. Sunlight has two components one is direct sunlight which reach to the ground without any change to the direction or intensity, second component is indirect or diffusion, which reaches to the ground after the so many reflection and scattering. Diffuse sunlight varies with a big range depends on the situation. If there is cloudless, the diffuse sunlight will be 10% of the total sunlight. The diffuse sunlight will be equal to the total sunlight if the sky cover with completely dark clouds and sun does not appear directly (Katardjiev, Iliia, 2020).

Sunlight is the basic parameter for the measurement of solar energy. Many methods including of the radiation and insolation are presented to measure sunlight with the using of either a pyrheliometer or pyranometer (Hoyt, Douglas V, 1979).

Radiation data for solar system to generate electricity is presented as kilowatt-hours per square and direct measurement data can be written, as watts per square meter. To convert solar energy into usable energy form like electricity or heat, some devices are used. Solar panel is used to collect sunlight, generate solar energy and convert into usable form such as electricity and heat. Over one hundred years ago, solar panels were used for water heating and solar photovoltaic panels are used to generate electricity. Sunlight collides with the panels and release energy into silicon layer, which is located between the two protector panels (Bollinger, et al, 2012).

Due to the absorption of sunlight energy, silicon atoms become excited and electrons move, which generate current. To concentrate sunlight onto specific location solar panels can be design with different shapes. Although pure silicon is the basic element for creation of the solar panels but combination of the silicon with other elements is also feasible with the consideration of negatively or positively charged solar panels. Combination of the silicon with phosphorus creates negatively plate and with the boron creates positively plate. For creation of the solar panels, these plates are sandwiched with conduction wire between them. The negatively plate is directed to the sunlight to absorb photons and electron knock off the outer band of the plate. Electron is drawn by positively plate into its own outer ring but this electron still does not free for long. As photons continuously hit negatively plate, more electrons are move and generate electricity (Weckend, et al, 2016).

The aim of this review paper is to collect understandable information regarding to the common functionalities and applications of the solar energy system.

Materials and methods

Many online and libraries advance textbooks, fresh sites of the physical institution and high journal publication articles have been studied for the conducting of this review paper. Sunlight was considered as the basic source for production of the solar energy. Common functionalities of the solar energy system with the usable materials such as silicon also put into consideration. Some common application of the solar energy in industries and common residential areas for water heating, electricity and water pumping have been studied. The above materials, which presented in this writing, have been collected from 23 international references.

Discussion

In today's era, energy is the most important part of the life. It has been tried to design and generate energy, which does not pollute environment, or create problem for human. Due to the shortcoming of fossil fuels, idea of the renewable energy came to the mind of scientists. This energy has been used in the form of electricity for 100 years. It is the nature energy and comes from rain, wind and sun. Among them solar energy is the most reliable to convert to electrical power. Solar energy plants with large power of MW are non-polluting, therefore, became more popular. The principle by which solar light converts to electricity is called photovoltaic. Meanwhile, amount of the electrical power is directly proportional to the sunlight intensity (Tudorache, et al, 2010).

Base on design, solar energy is divided into two types active and passive. Solar passive is a design with window to allow sunlight, pass onto thermal mass material for absorption, and store heat energy. Solar active has again two categories solar photovoltaic and solar thermal. Kramer junction, which located in California, has the largest plant of solar energy and generates 354 MW electrical power (Kolb, Gregory J, 1994).

In order to achieve the highest possible value of the solar energy, many scientists and researchers have payed attention to the investigation of the efficiency of PV system. Still now, three methods are presented to increase efficiency of the PV system. First method states, with the increasing of solar cell, second method refers to the conversion of energy, and third method to get maximum energy form sun (Cheung, et al, 2008).

Practically photovoltaic devices consist of a p-n junction, which develops photo voltage across the semiconductors. These devices are called solar cells. This semiconductor materials must be capable to absorb large amount of the sunlight spectrum on their surface. Absorption of the sunlight quanta generates electron hole pairs. If recombination does not happen, they will separate by electric field and reach to across the junction (Goetzberger, et al, 2003).

Solar energy is one of the renewable energy, which is clean and abundant everywhere on the world. It is also possible to convert solar energy into electrical or mechanical energy for the time demand with adequate

efficiency. For high efficiency of the solar energy system to design, the sunlight system is design to track on single axis with the azimuth angle and on two axes with the azimuth and zenith angles. To clear the tracking system, east-west part of the tracker is referred to horizontal tracking and angular height part of the tracker can be known as vertical tracking (Barsoum, Nader, 2011).

Recently, the solar trackers many types are available in markets such as passive and active, single axis and dual axis trackers. Each tracker has to be design to overcome requirement of the users. To build an effective desirable solar tracker these factors, cost, reliability, accuracy-sensor and efficiency must be considered as the main functionalities of the tracker. Cost is the very important component and must be put into consideration for the starting point of the project. In order to make solar tracker with low cost, used material must have high quality for design, which leads to the higher reliability and increasing of the lifetime. In addition, solar tracker must be located such away to be perpendicular to the sunlight at all times. For building of an efficient solar tracker, it is necessary to design an efficient algorithm to operate accurately the system (Amin, et al, 2008).

The most important component of the solar system for electrical solar system is solar panels that convert sunlight due to the photovoltaic effect directly into electricity. Solar panels output is measured by watt and has value between the 10 and 300 watts, but common configuration is 100 watts. Commonly, solar panels are arranged into arrays and mounted on roofs, poles in freestanding arrays or directly on the ground but the most common mounted system is roof mounted which is efficient and aesthetic but maintenance may be an issue for high roofs to clean or repair. Freestanding mounted maintenance may be easy but requires to occupy more space. Ground systems are simple but occupy more space and cannot be beneficial for regular snow falling areas. An array DC disconnect is used for maintenance to disconnect solar system from home. Using of an inverter is necessary to convert DC power into AC power because appliances use AC power and solar panels generate DC power. Solar system generates energy during the day with the shining of sun but demand of the energy is also for cloudy sky and night when sunlight is not appearing. To overcome this problem batteries are used in solar systems (Foss, Andrew, 2012).

There are three processes to turn sunlight into solar energy. Heliochemical, conversion is based on photosynthesis process, helioelectrical, conversion is based on photovoltaic process. Heliothermal, to convert sunlight into thermal energy base on solar power plants (Sarria, et al, 2005).

For utilization of all solar energy, these three functional steps must be exploited; capturing of the sunlight, conversion process and storage (Lewis, et al 2005).

Due to the commercially purposes, conversion has to be done by two ways. First way is photovoltaic effect, which convert sunlight directly into electricity and second way is thermal conversion such as residential space heating, hot water production and electricity generation (Crabtree, et al 2007).

The most common usable solar technologies for businesses and homes are passive solar design for cooling and heating of the space, solar water heating and photovoltaic effect for the generation of electricity. These technologies are used by industries and businesses for diversification of their energy sources and improvement of the efficiency. These technologies have been used to generate electricity with high rate to power small

towns and cities (Singh, H. N., and G. N. Tiwari, 2004).

One of the most common application of the solar energy is solar water heating system. This system is made from a black flat metal plate collector and metal tube, which located on the general direction of the sunlight. The collector plate is covered by a transparent glass and has in the beneath position a thermal insulation layer. The collector metal tube is connected to an insulated tank, which stores hot water during the cloudy day by a pipe. Hot water is provided into storage tank by metal tube. Water heating system is generally used in common places such as hotels, hospitals, guesthouses as well as for domestic purposes and space heating (Kalogirou, Soteris A, 2013).

Solar heating system can be used for heating of a building space. Recently, many ways are presented to heat space of a building such as collection of the sunlight directly by the some special elements of the building and enter to the space of the building. It mostly happen due to the reflection of sunlight. To use separately sunlight or solar collectors that can be able to heat either air, water or any storage devices. These devices must be able to accumulate the collected energy and to use on inclement days and at night. If a building requires heat, heat is transferred form collectors or storage devices to the space of the building by usable equipment such as hot air registers, fan etc. if heat does not require then heated water or air will be able to move to the heat storage devices as heat potential (Fuchs, R., and J. F. McClelland, 1979).

Solar-distillation system is applied in arid or coastal areas where is lacking of drinking water. The natural sunlight in these fields is used to convert saline water into distilled drinking water. In this process, sunlight is directed to enter to a basin which having saline water. Saline water is converted to potable distilled water and can be used in fields of scarcity such as colleges, hospitals, schools and defense labs. Solar distillation method is cheaper than every other distilled water method (Tiwari, G, et al, 2003).

Solar pumping system is commonly used for water pumping in irrigation fields. During the summer months, requirement for water pumping to the fields of irrigation is greatest but at the same period, solar radiation is increased. Therefore, this method is appropriate for irrigation purpose (Sontake, et al, 2016).

Solar energy is also used for drying purposes of the agricultural or animal products. Agricultural or animal products are placed in simple cupboard dryer, which covers with a transparent glass. Holes are generated at the top and bottom sides of the ventilator for flowing of the air over the placed material. The drying chilies methods by spreading materials on a floor requires wide-open space and labors for handling and also it is difficult to maintain its original quality but one of the way to overcome these problems is solar energy drying method (Fudholi, et al, 2014).

To study properties of the ceramic or produce nitric acid and fertilizers from air, high temperature is required and solar furnaces is used to provide this temperature. Heat can be stored without any contamination and this method is for especially for chemical and metallurgical operation (Haueter, et al, 1999).

Conclusion

A theoretical review base on the common functionalities and applications of the solar energy system has been reported. This work represents the basic source of the solar energy with the working principle and usable fields. Solar energy is one of the form of renewable energy, which is produced base on sunlight. Sunlight in the form of electromagnetic radiation goes through the atmosphere and reach to the earth surface. Calculation of the sunlight energy shows that it is more than the requirement of human but it has low density and depend on season, geographical location, local weather and time of the day. Solar panels are used to collect sun radiation, produce solar energy and turn into electrical or heating energy. For the increasing of the solar energy efficienc,y the solar panels must be design such a way to collect sunlight as much as possible. Because, amount of the solar energy is directly proportional to the intensity of sunlight. Moreover, efficiency of the solar energy can be increased with the increasing of solar cells, good conversion method and get maximum energy form sunlight. Solar system can be designed as passive or active system. Passive system does not need to any equipment but only thermal mass materials are used. Solar active system needs to some equipment to generate electricity or heat. In addition, to design an effective soar system these factors such as cost, accuracy-sensor, reliability and efficiency must be put into consideration. Solar energy are utilized in different fields such as industries or residential homes. Meanwhile, solar energy can be used depend on the requirement for water heating, heating of a building space, water distillation, water pumping, drying purposes of the animal or agriculture products and for generation of the high temperature.

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